

4. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 63.
5. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers Inc. New York, 1956, pp. 524, 537, 544.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, Green and Co. Ltd., London, 3rd. ed. p. 524.
7. K. K. DEB and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 178.
8. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
9. L. G. SILLEN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 185.

Dipole Moment of H-Bonded Complexes

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THE measurement of electric dipole moment gives valuable information on the bonding character of the complexes. The observed enhancement of dipole moment $\Delta\mu$ of H-bonded complexes,

$$\vec{\Delta\mu} = \left[\vec{\mu} \rightarrow (\text{complex})_{\text{expt}} - \sum \vec{\mu} \rightarrow \text{components} \right]$$

may be explained on the basis of proton-transfer and charge-transfer effects^{1,2}. The existing prototropic equilibrium depends on the concentration ranges of the acid and base involved, the self-association of either or both moieties and the formation of homoconjugate and heteroconjugate ions³. A number of correlations have been suggested between

$\Delta\mu$ and other physical properties of H-bonded complexes and its components, such as ionization potential⁴, dissociation constant^{1,5,6} and enthalpy

of formation². Ratajczak et al¹ found that $\Delta\mu$ in triethylamine-phenol complexes in non-polar solvents changes continuously within a wide range from 0.30 to about 10.00 D. To account such high polarity they suggested the possibility of partial proton-transfer species with an equilibrium of type

The potential energy curve has two minima, one near the atom O and the other near the atom N and the proton oscillates between them⁷. Vinogradov and Linnell pointed out from conductimetric data that such partial proton transfer complexes are appreciably more stable than true ion pairs.

In the present study the influence of both inductive and tautomeric effects on the strength and polarity of H-bonds is analysed. The interaction moment $\Delta\mu$ for five complexes between phenols as proton

donors and triethylamine as proton acceptor has been determined by employing the dielectric variation method⁹. The experiments as previously described¹⁰ were carried out at phenol concentrations 0.01-0.1 mole per litre, where the association of the phenol molecules among themselves is negligibly small. From these experimental values and those calculated by vectorial additivity of the dipolar moments of the moieties, the interaction moment

$\Delta\mu$ along O-H...N axis has been estimated under certain tacit assumptions: the nitrogen lone pair orbital is directed along the hydrogen bond, i.e., the C_{3v} axis of the triethylamine coincides with the O-H...N axis, the COH angle for phenols is assumed to be 115° and the dipole moment of O-H bond in phenol is taken as 1.76 D and the free rotation around the O-H...N axis in the complexes studied. Considering the length of the hydrogen bond as the reference axis, the direction in which the dipole moments μ_a and μ_b acting can be represented as α° and β° respectively with respect to the O-H...N axis. Then $\Delta\mu$ can be expressed as

$$\Delta\mu = \pm \sqrt{\mu_{ab}^2 - \mu_a^2 \sin^2 \alpha - \mu_b^2 \sin^2 \beta - 2\mu_a \mu_b \sin \alpha \sin \beta - \mu_a \cos \alpha - \mu_b \cos \beta}$$

The results obtained are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $\Delta\mu$ FOR TRIETHYLAMINE-PHENOLS COMPLEXES

Phenol derivative	$\mu_b = 0.90\text{D}$		$\beta^\circ = 0$		$\Delta\mu$	pK_a
	μ_a	α°	μ_{complex}			
			Present work	From literature**		
<i>p</i> -cresol	1.58	26°42'	2.79	2.73	0.39	10.26
<i>m</i> -cresol	1.54	25°28'	2.70	...	0.23	10.04
Phenol	1.63	22°48'	3.05	2.96	0.58	9.95
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	2.14	24°12'	3.82	...	0.87	9.42
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	2.25	24°54'	4.01	4.07	0.95	9.08

μ values are expressed on Debye units.

* A. Koli, H. Ratajczak and I. Sobczyk, *Roczn. Chem.*, 1970, **44**, 825.

** Reference 1.

*** G. Kortum, W. Vogel and K. Andrussov, "Dissociation Constants of Organic acids in Aqueous Solution", Butterworths, London, 1961.

Since $\Delta\mu$ is ≤ 1.0 D in the complexes studied, the interacting components of the present system form H-bonds of type O-H...N and the possibility of formation of proton-transfer complex is negligibly small.

However, the increase of $\Delta\mu$ with increasing acid strength of the phenol (fall in pK_a) can only be interpreted on the basis of proton-transfer effect, which becomes more and more predominant as pK_a falls

off. The result of the present work is in good agreement with the theoretical prediction based on the formal proton-transfer model suggested by Huyskens and Zeegers Huyskens¹¹ and the experimental study on the dependence of the polarity of the hydrogen bond on the properties of the hydrogen donor¹²⁻¹⁴.

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References

1. H. RATAJCZAK and L. SOBCZYK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, **50**, 556.
2. H. RATAJCZAK and W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **58**, 911.
3. R. A. HUDSON, R. M. SCOTT and S. N. VINOGRADOV, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1989.
4. H. RATAJCZAK, *J. Phys., Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 3991.
5. L. SOBCZYK and Z. PAWELHA, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans I.*, 1974, **70**, 832.
6. G. DEBECKER and P. HUYSKENS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1971, **68**, 295.
7. H. ZIMMERMANN, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1964, **3**, 157.
8. S. N. VINOGRADOV and R. H. LINNELL, "Hydrogen bonding", p. 168, 1971, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, London.
9. A. W. FEW and J. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2781.
10. V. SHANMUGASUNDARAM and M. MEYVAPPAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 936.
11. P. HUYSKENS and TH. ZEEGERS-HUYSKENS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **61**, 81.
12. J. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **61**, 126.
13. K. BAUGE and J. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, A, 616.
14. L. SOBCZYK and J. K. SYRKIN, *Rozn. Chem.*, 1956, **30**, 881, 898; 1957, **31**, 197, 204, 1245.

Viscosity Molecular Weight Relationship for Solvent Polyoxyethyleneglycol Systems

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STUDIES have been reported on the intrinsic viscosity of some polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions by Mueh¹ at one temperature, but so far no systematic attempt has been made to investigate the viscometric behaviour of these fractions at different temperatures. The intrinsic viscosities of polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions (ranging in molecular weights from 400 to 1540) have, therefore, been

measured in benzene and water at 30°, 35° and 40°. Relationship between intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight has been discussed.

Experimental

Benzene used was of B.D.H. AR grade. Conductivity water was prepared by distilling thrice distilled water with alkaline potassium permanganate. The polyoxyethylene fractions were quite pure except for their tendency to absorb moisture which was removed by prolonged evacuation of the samples before use.

Ubbelohde type² capillary viscometer was used for viscosity measurements. The accuracy in time of flow was ± 0.1 sec. The densities were determined pycnometrically, accuracy being ± 5 parts in 10^5 . Kinetic energy correction was applied to the viscosity data and accuracy was found to be ± 7 parts in 10^4 .

Results

The values of intrinsic viscosity obtained from the extrapolation of the plots of η_{sp}/C vs. C and $\ln \eta_r/C$ vs C are given in Table 1. A survey of the data

Mol. Wt. (M)	Polymer-Benzene Systems [η] (ml/gm)		
	30°	35°	40°
400	2.40	2.38	1.96
1000	4.43	4.35	4.25
1500	5.34	4.90	4.28
1540	6.48	5.94	5.57
	Polymer-Water Systems		
	30°	35°	40°
400	3.37	1.66	0.70
1000	5.10	4.39	2.48
1500	6.58	6.11	2.64
1540	8.03	7.30	3.56

reveals the following facts :

(i) The intrinsic viscosity increases with an increase in molecular weight of the polymer and decreases with the rise in temperature in both the solvents.

(ii) Water may be considered a better solvent for polyoxyethyleneglycol than benzene at 30° and 35°. The results agree with the published data of Lakanpal et al³, on the heat of mixing of these polyglycol-solvent systems.

(iii) The rapid fall of intrinsic viscosity for the polymer-water systems at 40° indicates the disruption of solute-solvent interactions, thereby showing that water is better solvent than benzene even at 40°.